

How tilting a vessel containing a fissile solution influences its reactivity

Jean-Sébastien Borrod*

Université Paris-Saclay, CEA, Service d'Études des Réacteurs et de Mathématiques Appliquées, 91191, Gif-sur-Yvette, France.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804098

ABSTRACT

The way a criticality accident occurred on January 2nd, 1958, in a nuclear processing plant located in Mayak (Russia), inspired the work described in this article: three experimenters tilted a tank in order to empty the drop of fissile solution contained in the latter, which triggered off a sudden excursion taking a tragic turn. Therefore, we studied the link existing between the tilt and the reactivity of fissile systems similar to the above-mentioned one. We could: assess, with an up-to-date neutronics code, the ability of such assemblies to cause a criticality accident; bring to the fore how this ability is related to a geometric parameter depending on the tilt of the tank. Thus, this article gives once more the opportunity to emphasize one of the dangers associated with the handling of fissile solutions (such as those devoted to experimental reactors), since the shape of the latter may change very easily.

Keywords. Fissile solution; cylindrical tank; tilt; reactivity

1. INTRODUCTION

The subject matter of this article is the connection existing between, on the one hand, the reactivity of a cylindrical tank, partially filled with a fissile solution, and possibly surrounded by a reflector, and on the other hand, the tilt of this tank with respect to a fixed plane (a horizontal one, for example). This study was undertaken by examining such a situation which arose in a fuel processing plant, and which led the reactivity of the involved system to grow high enough, to cause an accidental excursion in the latter (Section 2). In the following, we first and foremost focus on the calculation of the effective multiplication factor of specific fissile assemblies (described in Section 3), i.e. on their ability or inability to keep a chain reaction going (see Sections 4.1 and 4.2).

2. CRITICALITY ACCIDENT, WHICH OCCURRED ON JANUARY 2ND, 1958, IN MAYAK PROCESSING PLANT

The starting point of this study is the course of an excursion, that experimenters underwent, during their work in Mayak production Centre (Russia). Many criticality accidents punctuated the first years of this factory, in which several nuclear fuels are processed: from 1953 to 1968, 7 such events happened over there. After the second unintended excursion, the plant authorities made the decision to order a series of measurements, to prevent high concentration, highly enriched uranyl nitrate solutions to exceed criticality, when they were handled in tanks with an unfavourable geometry. Thanks to the experimental

*jean-sebastien.borrod@cea.fr

equipment devised, it was possible to determine the critical parameters of the different vessels used in the factory. After each experiment, the tank could be safely emptied, through side pipes driving the fissile solution into favourable geometry bottles, with a 6 litres maximum volume. The first series of measurements were performed during the last two months of the year 1957. Then, the persons in charge decided to focus on a larger vessel: thus, they had a stainless steel cylindrical tank, with a 75 cm inside diameter, put on the stand, and the first experiment with this container was carried out on January 2nd, 1958, after a holiday period. Once this work was completed, it was time to drain the fissile solution. At first, the procedure described above was followed, but it was circumvented as soon as the layer of fissile solution remaining in the tank was considered as sufficiently thin. Once this height of solution dropped to 13.2 cm (i.e. once the ratio "height / (inside diameter)" was equal to $0.176 \ll 1$), the experimenters thought they could save time by directly decanting this small amount of fuel left, from the vessel into 6 l bottles. Performing this operation was easy, because the studied tank was only bolted on a steel stand. When the vessel was removed, three members of the team could lift it, in order to try and pour its contents into the 6 l bottles, as it is shown in the following figure. At that moment, a criticality accident occurred, and proved so violent, that it means that the fissile system in which it started had exceeded prompt criticality: during this event, some solution was thrown out of the tank, up to the ceiling located 5 m above it. Since the fuel was scattered, the reactivity of the system fell, so that this unintended excursion came to an end after one single power pulse. Nevertheless, this excursion was intense enough (according to a later evaluation, it generated 2×10^{17} fissions ≈ 6.06 MJ), to seriously and instantaneously irradiate 4 workers.

Operation during which a criticality accident happened, on January 2nd, 1958:

One single power pulse: $N_f = 2 \times 10^{17}$ fissions.
 $\rho > 1 \text{ \$}$ at the beginning of the excursion.

The solution was suddenly ejected, up to the ceiling, situated 5 m above the tank.

• 3 employees lifted and tilted the vessel → each of them was exposed to (60 ± 20) Gy → they died in 5 to 6 days.

• 1 member of the staff, who was 2.5 m away from the tank, absorbed 6 Gy → she suffered from persistent health problems, such as cataract and blindness a few years later.

Figure 1: Configuration which led to an unwanted excursion in Mayak, on January 2nd, 1958.

Thus, by working with a view to avoiding future criticality accidents, this team triggered off one of these feared events: it makes the final toll of the disaster all the more cruel. As for the physical phenomena that led to this tragedy by making the system more reactive, they are clearly visible above:

1. At the beginning, the fissile solution had an elongated shape, making it easier for the neutrons to leave the system without colliding with nuclei, and therefore curbing the growth of a chain reaction. Then, the solution became gradually more compact, i.e. more reactive. When some nuclear fuel is in solution, its geometry may change very easily: this is one of the main reasons why a criticality accident is particularly feared in such configurations;
2. The way the fissile material was reflected and moderated evolved, when three experimenters lifted the tank by seizing it bodily. Since a human being is made up of 65 % of water, a person weighing 70 kg contains 45 litres of this liquid, for example. Consequently, the three workers served as a reflector and a moderator around the solution: they contributed to send neutrons

back into it, and these neutrons had a greater ability to generate fissions, than when they had left the fuel.

In the following, we aim at assessing these qualitative observations, and especially the link existing between the reactivity and the geometry of the fissile solution, i.e. the link between the reactivity and the tilt of the tank with respect to a horizontal plane.

3. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDIED CONFIGURATIONS

In order to reach this goal, the systems that are modelled below, are based on the circumstances of the criticality accident mentioned previously.

3.1. Fissile System: Solutions, Vessel and its Surroundings

Thus, two fissile solutions were successively considered: an uranyl nitrate solution ($\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$), containing 100 g(total U)/l, with an uranium enrichment equal to 90 %; a plutonium nitrate solution ($\text{Pu}(\text{NO}_3)_4$), containing 100 g(total Pu)/l, with the following isotopic percentages (^{239}Pu : 87.4 % ; ^{240}Pu : 8.8 % ; ^{241}Pu : 3.8 %). The fissile solutions were modelled in an open cylindrical tank, with an inside radius $R = 37.5$ cm, an inside height $L = 100$ cm, and walls 0.2 cm ($= e$) thick and made of steel.

Figure 2: Cross (left) and axial (right) sectional views of the vessel, surrounded by water.

We assumed that, before the tank was unbolted, it stood on the centre of a square plate made of the same steel, its side being 100 cm in length, and its thickness being equal to 0.8 cm. After the dissociation of the stand from the tank, the latter was modelled with a varying tilt (see the next paragraph), and: wrapped in air only, in order to assess how this sole tilt influences the reactivity; or surrounded by water, as it is shown in the 2 previous sectional views. Thus, the reflection and the moderation from the three experimenters who grabbed the vessel, is also taken into account in a conservative manner. Consequently, the bottom (respectively side wall) of the tank was lined with a water layer 2.5 cm (respectively 20 cm) thick, to simulate the hands (respectively bodies) of the carriers at that place.

3.2. Height of the Fissile Solution Surface, in the Tilted Tank

Concerning the volume V of fissile solution contained in the vessel: all the configurations of the tilted tank that were studied, are associated with the same volume, equal to the initial one. Thus, throughout the calculations, we prevented a fuel volume equal to $V = \pi R^2 H \approx 58.316$ litres ($H = 13.2$ cm), from spilling over out of the tank, by bounding its tilt between the vertical (i.e. $\alpha = 90^\circ$), and the limit angle α_{lim} drawn in the following Figure 3.

Figure 3: Axial sectional views of the vessel containing fissile solution, when its tilt varies.

Figure 4: Axial sectional views, used to calculate the height of the fissile solution surface, with respect to point O. $L_t = 0$ for one of the tilts, and $L_t \neq 0$ for the other one.

Then, in order to model the whole system, it was necessary to calculate the height of the fissile solution surface, with respect to the chosen origin O of the coordinates: the centre of the inside wall of the tank. According to the previous axial sectional views of the system (Figure 4), this height equals:

$$\left(L_f - \frac{L}{2}\right) \times \sin(\alpha) - R \times \cos(\alpha) \tag{1}$$

where L_f (= maximum length of the side wall, which is covered with solution, in the vertical plane including the (Oz') axis) was determined as follows. First, we assume that the tank is tilted enough for its bottom to be only partially covered with solution (i.e. $\alpha \leq \alpha_1 = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{R}{H}\right) \approx 70.608^\circ$, according to the previously chosen data), and that the container is not too tilted, for the fuel to stay inside (it yields: $\alpha \geq \alpha_{lim} \approx 14.902^\circ$). In such a configuration, since the solution volume V is known ($V = \pi R^2 H$), it is possible to choose a set of values for the angle α , and to infer the associated length L_f , from the numerical resolution (by the use of dichotomy, for example) of the equation below:

$$\frac{R^3}{\tan(\alpha)} \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(2 + \left(1 - \frac{L_f \times \tan(\alpha)}{R} \right)^2 \right) \sqrt{1 - \left(1 - \frac{L_f \times \tan(\alpha)}{R} \right)^2} - \left(1 - \frac{L_f \times \tan(\alpha)}{R} \right) \times \text{Arccos} \left(1 - \frac{L_f \times \tan(\alpha)}{R} \right) \right] = \pi R^2 H \tag{2}$$

Next, we assume that the bottom of the cylindrical tank is entirely covered with solution, i.e. $\alpha_1 < \alpha \leq 90^\circ$. In such a situation, L_f and α are linked by the relationship below:

$$L_f = H + \frac{R}{\tan(\alpha)} \tag{3}$$

N.B.: The previous equations (2) and (3) were obtained by expressing the solution volume V , as a function of the tilt α of the tank containing it.

4. EVALUATION OF THE REACTIVITY OF THE CONSIDERED SYSTEM, IN DIFFERENT CONFIGURATIONS

Then, the multiplication factor k_{eff} of the previously described assemblies, was calculated with the three-dimensional, continuous energy TRIPOLI-4.11® code, based on the Monte-Carlo method, and associated with the CEA V512 nuclear data library. We chose to bound the maximum standard deviation value σ , which is linked to the calculation uncertainty, by 100 pcm. To sum up, the configurations that were successively modelled, hold $V = 58.316$ litres of firstly an uranyl nitrate solution, secondly a plutonium nitrate solution, contained in the vertical tank, simply resting on its steel stand; or in the tank surrounded only by air, or by water, its tilt ranging from $\alpha_{\text{lim}} \approx 14.902^\circ$ to 90° with respect to a horizontal plane. In the following section (4.1), we focus on the uranyl nitrate solution case, for example.

4.1. Case of an Uranyl Nitrate Solution: Results

4.1.1. Container = vertical tank simply resting on its steel stand

The calculations performed in this configuration, led to the results presented in the table below. The latter show that the considered assembly was undoubtedly sub-critical before it was unbolting. In addition, the critical height of the solution was evaluated in such a case: it reaches 14.95 cm, which corresponds to a volume equal to 66.047 litres.

Table I. TRIPOLI-4.11® calculation results, vessel (with $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$) resting vertically on its stand.

Angle: α (°)	$(k_{\text{eff}}+3\sigma)$	Reactivity: ρ (\$)	β_{eff} (pcm)
90	0.915	-10.81	859

4.1.2. Container = tank surrounded by air or water, with a tilt ranging from α_{lim} to 90°

The results associated with these two types of configurations, are presented below.

Table II. Tilts making the assembly critical or prompt critical, when the tank (containing an $(\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2)$ solution) is surrounded by water, or wrapped in air only.

	Reactivity ρ (\$) evaluated with Mean(β_{eff}) (= 792 pcm if vessel lined with water; = 821 pcm with no peripheral reflector)	Vessel lined with water (below and laterally)		Vessel with no peripheral reflector	
		Angle α (°)	$(k_{\text{eff}}+3\sigma)$	Angle α (°)	$(k_{\text{eff}}+3\sigma)$
Criticality	0	86.560	1	75.786	1
Prompt criticality	1	85.318	1.00798	74.957	1.00828
Angular gap between criticality and prompt criticality (°)		1.242		0.829	
Local slope of the curve [$\rho=f(\alpha)$] (\$/°)		0.81		1.21	
Angular range over which the system exceeds criticality (°)		71.658		60.884	
Initial period of an excursion which would start when $\alpha = 85^\circ$ (lined with water) / 74° (no periph. reflect.) (ms)		16.021		2.970	

Figure 5: $\rho = f(\alpha)$, when the tank (with $UO_2(NO_3)_2$) is wrapped in air, or surrounded by water.

4.2. Observations

4.2.1. Influences, on the reactivity of the examined system, of the tilt of the vessel, and of a water layer lining the vessel walls: a comparison

The previous sections set out that if the vertical tank, containing a drop of fissile solution, is surrounded by a water layer, then such an assembly does not exceed criticality. In addition, if the vessel is tilted by an angle α ranging from 14.902° to 90° with respect to a horizontal plane, lining its walls with a water layer brings an additional reactivity bounded by 6.78 \$ to 15.23 \$ (respectively 18.82 \$ to 41.84 \$), to the system, if it holds uranyl (respectively plutonium) nitrate. On the contrary, tilting the tank causes the shape of the solution contained in it to vary: this phenomenon may bring up to 24.48 \$ (vessel surrounded by water) or 32.70 \$ (vessel wrapped in air only) in the uranyl nitrate configuration, or up to 64.42 \$ (water) or 86.42 \$ (air) in the plutonium nitrate configuration. Consequently, the fact that the reactivity of such a system can rise, is above all caused by the tilt of the vessel. The reflection and moderation effects, brought by the surrounding water, mainly cause the k_{eff} level, at which an accidental excursion may begin, to rise even more (i.e. this contribution may make this excursion even more brutal), and widen the α angular domain in which such an event may occur.

4.2.2. A breakdown of the link existing between α and ρ

Besides, the tilt (α) domain in which the system exceeds criticality, proves very wide, in the different studied configurations: this width ranges from 60.884° (tank wrapped in air only) to 71.658° (tank surrounded by water) with uranyl nitrate (Fig. 5), or from 55.022° (air) to 65.887° (water) with plutonium nitrate. Therefore, this assembly is a high-risk one, in the field of criticality accidents. In addition, when the system is near criticality, its reactivity ρ proves very sensitive to the tilt α of the tank. The absolute value of the local slope of the curve representing ρ as a function of α , actually ranges from 0.81 $\$/^\circ$ (water) to 1.21 $\$/^\circ$ (air) with uranyl nitrate, and from 2.36 $\$/^\circ$ (water) to 2.58 $\$/^\circ$ (air) with plutonium nitrate. Consequently, a small variation in the tilt of the vessel is enough to make the assembly go from criticality to prompt criticality: the gap existing between these two states does not exceed 0.829° (air) to

1.242° (water) with uranyl nitrate; these values drop to 0.388° (air) to 0.424° (water) with plutonium nitrate. In other words, there is only a very little angular gap, between a configuration of the container, that may lead to a criticality accident beginning slowly (i.e. it would be controllable if detected), and a situation prompting a sudden excursion, with consequences that would be anyway unstoppable. We recall that an accident with a slow (respectively sudden) start, has an initial period with an order of magnitude reaching several hundreds of seconds at least (respectively about ten milliseconds).

4.2.3. Angular domain in which the reactivity of the system peaks

By having a close look at the results presented at the beginning of section 4, we also note down the following observation: no matter the vessel is wrapped in air or surrounded by water, all the considered assemblies reach their maximum reactivity in the same angular domain, i.e. around 40° (the result is identical with plutonium nitrate). This tilt which makes ρ reach its highest point, is shown in Figure 4 (left side). No matter the tilt of the tank with respect to a horizontal plane, there is no denying that the fissile solution is always quite widely spread in it. The following graph (Figure 6), displaying the maximum horizontal extent of the fuel $MAX(E_{horiz})$ (evaluated analytically, in the vertical plane encompassing the tank central axis (Oz')) as a function of the tilt α , illustrates that $MAX(E_{horiz})$ always exceeds 65.62 cm, i.e. 87.49 % of the container diameter $2R$. On the other hand, when α verges on 40°, the depth $L_f \cdot \sin(\alpha)$ of the fissile solution can reach up to around 33 cm just above the lowest point of the tank, which makes up roughly the half of $MAX(E_{horiz})$. It means that, in such a configuration, the fuel locally has the most condensed shape possible in this tank: therefore, the interaction probability between neutrons and fissile nuclei, peaks at that place. In other words, the reactivity locally reaches its highest possible level, which affects the reactivity of the global system. Consequently, it can be noted that the different curves " $\rho = f(\alpha)$ " plotted previously, look similar to the new one below (Figure 7), showing the maximum depth " $L_f \cdot \sin(\alpha)$ " of the solution, as a function of the tilt α : all these curves are alike, as far as the way they vary, or their relative values, are concerned.

Figure 6: Maximum horizontal extent of the solution, as a function of α .

N.B.: On the contrary, the morphology of the solution as a whole is not sufficiently correlated to its reactivity, in order to aptly set out how ρ depends on α , in the entire domain $[\alpha_{lim}; 90^\circ]$. The following graph (Figure 8) illustrates this observation, by showing the ratio $V/S_{ext} = \text{Solution volume} / \text{Solution outer area} = f(\alpha)$, where S_{ext} was calculated analytically. When the tank, initially vertical, is gradually tilted, the solution contained in it tends to spread more and more (i.e. V/S_{ext} decreases), whereas ρ rises in this angular domain. Similarly, when α comes close to α_{lim} , the solution is more stretched than in its vertical cylindrical configuration (i.e. $(V/S_{ext})(\alpha \rightarrow \alpha_{lim}) < (V/S_{ext})(\alpha = 90^\circ)$); nonetheless, $\rho(\alpha \rightarrow \alpha_{lim}) > 0 > \rho(\alpha = 90^\circ)$. Even so, ρ peaks in the same angular domain (α roughly equal to 40°) as the V/S_{ext} ratio: it means that the reactivity of the assembly is really maximum, when the fuel comes to the most condensed shape possible in this tank, i.e. when the neutron leakage area is minimum.

Figure 7: Maximum depth of the solution, as a function of α .

Figure 8: Ratio $V/S_{ext} = f(\alpha)$.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This article investigates the type of criticality accident that happened in 1958, in the Russian factory located in Mayak, when 3 workers endeavoured to empty quickly a fissile solution contained in a vessel, by tilting it. So, we studied the link between the tilt of a tank (which results in an evolution of the shape of the solution) and the reactivity of such systems: thus, we could quantify the potential they have, which amounts to a few tens of \$, to launch an unwanted excursion. These assemblies can remain beyond criticality in angular domains that extend over several tens of °, whereas they are quite below this state when the vessel is vertical. **Besides, it is interesting to notice that, among the geometric data that can be calculated to characterize the morphology of a liquid contained in a tilted tank, it is the maximum depth of this liquid, which has the closest behaviour to that of reactivity, if the variation of these 2 parameters is plotted as a function of the tilt of the vessel.** Moreover, the reactivity of such systems may vary very rapidly with their tilt (at a rate in the region of 1 \$/°), especially if they are close to criticality, which means that only a few tenths of degrees may separate criticality from prompt criticality, and thus change completely the way an excursion may begin in it. This variety of accidental scenarios, which may easily lead to the worst of them, is especially fearsome if the involved fissile assembly intrinsically lacks neutrons, like those that contain uranium only: then, since an excursion may need a waiting period to begin, the reactivity may have time to rise significantly, which may trigger off an even more violent event. To conclude, this article focused on one of the main causes leading to criticality accidents in fissile solutions: the fact that the shape of the fuel may easily change, which favours the interactions between neutrons and nuclei, and then constitutes a genuine hazard.